

APPENDIX

A. FADN VARIABLE DESCRIPTION

The following table presents the original variable names and descriptions as defined by DG AGRI for the various outcome determinants (left column) and treatment determinants (right column) used in this study.

Table A.1: Variables included in the treatment determinants (X_{TD}) and outcome determinants (X_{OD}) sets

Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
SE621	Environmental subsidies	ACSHEQ_CV	Cash and equivalents Closing Value
SORGSUB_2_V	Organic farming subsidy. Value (subsidy co-financed by the EU and the Member State)	AASBIO_DY	Biological assets - plants Depreciation of the current year Value
NUTS2	NUTS2 region	AASBIO_SV	Biological assets - plants Sales Value
SN2000SUB_2_V	Natura 2000 payments excl. forestry Value (subsidy co-financed by the EU and the Member State)	ACURASOTH_CV	Other current assets Closing Value
CLUAA	Classes of area sizes	AFRMBLD_DY	Farm buildings Depreciation of the current year Value
SE010	Total labour input	AFRMBLD_SV	Farm buildings Sales Value
LEGAL	Legal status Table A, General info	AINTNTRAS_IP	Intangible assets, non-tradable Investment/Purchase, before deduction of subsidies Value
SYS04	Exchange rate to EUR from (former) national currency	AINTTRAS_CV	Intangible assets, tradable Closing Value
SE132	Total output / Total input	AINTTRAS_SV	Intangible assets, tradable Sales Value
LCOWDAIR_PI	Dairy cows. Price index	AINVNTS_SUB	Inventories Subsidies Value
TYPOWN	Type of ownership/economic objective Table A, General info	ALNDAGR_OV	Agricultural land Opening Value

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
OFRSTPRS_FCV	Forestry and wood processing Farmhouse consumption Value	ALNDFRSTST_IP	Forest land including standing timber Investment/Purchase, before deduction of subsidies Value
SAGRPRCTCL IMENVSUBGR_T	Agricultural pract. beneficial for climate and environment greening subsidy. Type of compliance with the greening practices	ALNDIMP_AD	Land improvements Accumulated depreciation Value
LGOATBRE_PI	Goats, breeding fem. Price index	ALNDIMP_OV	Land improvements Opening Value
TF8	Type of Farming TF8 (see RICC 1750)	AMCHQP_AD	Machinery and equipment Accumulated depreciation Value
SE105	Table chickens, laying hens and other poultry.	AMCHQP_OV	Machinery and equipment Opening Value
ACCTYP	Type of accounting Table A, General info	ANC3	Grouping of LFA and ANC areas in 3 classes
LHENSLAY_PI	Laying hens Price index	ANCURASOTH_IP	Other non-current assets Investment/Purchase, before Deduction of subsidies Value
LPLTRBROYL_PI	Table chickens Price index	ARECV_CV	Receivables Closing Value
QSPSXSPLRTIN_P	Entitlements for payments under single payment scheme except special rights Payments for quota leased or rented in quota, value	CAPL_IRA	Apples Irrigated area
ID SPERMGRSN 2000_T	Unique Identifier Of which env. sensitive perm. grassland in Natura 2000 greening subsidy. Type of compliance with the greening practices	CAPL_SQ	Apples Sales Quantity
		CARALNDSSED_A	Seeds and seedlings Area

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
		<i>Continued from previous page</i>	
ALNDFRSTST_CV	Forest land including standing timber Closing Value	CARALNDSSED_OV	Seeds and seedlings Opening Value
LTOTANIM_ON	Total animals. Opening number	CARALNDSSED_TA	Seeds and seedlings Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
VMASYS_C	Main VAT system in the farm VAT systems in the farm VAT system	CARAOTH_OV	Other arable land crops Opening Value
NAT2000	Natura 2000 area Table A, General info	CARAOTH_TO	Other arable land crops Total output Value
ALTITUDE	Altitude zone Table A, General info	CBERRY_IRTA	Berries (excluding strawberries) Irrigated total area (incl as follow up-crop)
SIZ6	Economic size class (6 classes)	CBERRY_SV	Berries (excluding strawberries) Sales Value
SYS02	Sum of weighting coefficients of individual holdings in the sample (=sampil farm's weight for individual farms)	CBRL_CV	Barley Closing Value
CTOTGRASS_TO	Grass output value	CBRL_OV	Barley Opening Value
CSNFL_TA	Sunflower seed Total area (incl as follow up-crop)	CBRL_TA	Barley Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
SE446	Agricultural land, permanent crops, improvements to land, quotas and other prescribed rights (including acquisition costs) and forest land.	CBYOTH_PRQ	Other by-products Production Quantity
CSNFL_A	Sunflower seed Area	CCEROTH_CV	Triticale, sorghum and other cereals n.e.c. (buckwheat, millet, canary seed, etc.) Closing Value

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
			<i>Continued from previous page</i>
SE022	Share of OGA work in AWU, in percent	CCEROTH_IRA	Triticale, sorghum and other cereals n.e.c. (buckwheat, millet, canary seed, etc.) Irrigated area
SANC_2_V	Payment for areas with natural constraints subsidy. Value (subsidy co-financed by the EU and the Member State)	CCEROTH_SQ	Triticale, sorghum and other cereals n.e.c. (buckwheat, millet, canary seed, etc.) Sales Quantity
CGRSTMP_FUV	Temporary grasses and grazings Farm use Value	CCFL_A	Cauliflower and broccoli Area
LTOTANIM_ALU	Total livestock - Livestock unit	CCITRFRUT_PRQ	Citrus orch. Quantity
ICAR_V	Car expenses Labour and machinery costs and inputs Value	CCOMPSCR_PSV	Compensation by crop insurance not allocable to specific crops Sales Value
SE622	LFA subsidies.	CCOTN_OV	Cotton Opening Value
SE490	Loans contracted for a period of more than one year.	CCOTN_TA	Cotton Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
CWHTC_FUV	Common wheat and spelt Farm use Value	CCRNSWT_IRA	Sweet corn Irrigated area
SE115	Yield of maize	CCRNSWT_SQ	Sweet corn Sales Quantity
WURHNM_Y1_TOT	Unpaid regular,Holder/not managerTOT,Total annual time worked (hours)	CCRPBY_CV	Crop by-products other than from olives and vine Closing Value
WATDIR	Water directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) area	CCRPBY_PSV	Crop by-products other than from olives and vine Sales Value
LEWEBRE_PI	Ewes Price index	CCRPINDOTH_IRTA	Energy and other industrial crops n.e.c. Irrigated total area (incl as follow up-crop)
CGRSTMP_TO	Temporary grasses and grazings Total output Value	CCRPOILOTH_A	Other oil seed crops n.e.c. Area

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
SPLTSOIL SUB_3_V	Olive plantations subsidies Value (not financed from the EU budget but by other public sources)	CCRPOILOTH _PRQ	Other oil seed crops n.e.c. Production Quantity
SCRPINDSUB LEG_1_V	Industrial crops subsidy: Grain legumes. Value (subsidy financed solely from the EU budget)	CCRPPROTOTH_A	Other protein crops Area
CTOTGRASS_CV	Grass closing value	CCRPPROTOTH _PRQ	Other protein crops Production Quantity
LHENSLAY_SSV	Laying hens Sales for slaughtering Value	CFIBOTH_A	Other fibre crops n.e.c. Area
CBRL_FUV	Barley Farm use Value	CFLND_SV	Fallow land without any subsidies Sold
LBUFDAIRPRS_PI	Buffalo cows. Price index	CFODMZ_ENA	Green maize Energy crop area
SNHNDMNT SUB_2_V	Payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints (ANC, LFA) Value (subsidy co-financed by the EU and the Member State)	CFODMZ_PRQ	Green maize Production Quantity
COLVOIL_A	Olive oil Area	CFODOOTH_CV	Other plants and cereals (excluding green maize) harvested green n.e.c. Closing Value
DCOMSTDLT_OV	Debt Commercial standard Long term opening value	CGRLC_CV	Garlic Closing Value
ACSHEQ_OV	Cash and equivalents Opening Value	CGRLC_SV	Garlic Sales Value
SE251	Other livestock & products	CGRPTAB_IRA	Grapes for table use Irrigated area
OGASHARE	Other gainful activities directly related to the holding Table A, General info	CGRPTAB_SQ	Grapes for table use Sales Quantity

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
		<i>Continued from previous page</i>	
SBPS_1_V	BPS (Basic payment scheme) subsidy. Value (subsidy financed solely from the EU budget)	CGRPWINOTH_A	Grapes for other wines Area
SCRPCATCH_N	EFA Areas with catch crops. Number of basic units (in hectares)	CGRPWINOTH_OV	Grapes for other wines Opening Value
SOTHEXCP SUB_3_V	Other grants and subsidies of exceptional character Value (not financed from the EU budget but by other public sources)	CGRPWINOTH_TA	Grapes for other wines Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
LHENSLAY_SSN	Laying hens Sales for slaughtering Number	CGRPWIN PDO_IRA	Grapes for wine with protected designation of origin (PDO) Irrigated area
LCOWDAIR_SSV	Dairy cows Sales for slaughtering Value	CGRPWINPDO_SQ	Grapes for wine with protected designation of origin (PDO) Sales Quantity
SANIMSUBDP OTH_1_V	Other coupled payments not mentioned elsewhere. Value (subsidy financed solely from the EU budget)	CGRPWINPGI_A	Grapes for wine with protected geographical indication (PGI) Area
SE624	Total support for rural development	CGRPWINPGI_OV	Grapes for wine with protected geographical indication (PGI) Opening Value
IPLTRFEDFPR_V	Farm-produced feedstuffs for poultry and other small animals Specific livestock costs Value	CGRPWINPGI_TA	Grapes for wine with protected geographical indication (PGI) Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
SSFS_V	Small farmers scheme Subsidy Value	CGRSTMP_PRQ	Temporary grasses and grazings Production Quantity

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Outcome determinants		Treatment determinants	
Name in FADN dataset	Description	Name in FADN dataset	Description
		<i>Continued from previous page</i>	
SE027	Permanent crops	CGRSXRG_CV	Pasture and meadow, excluding rough grazings Closing Value
SE042	Energy crops. Area	CGRSXRG_OV	Pasture and meadow, excluding rough grazings Opening Value
SE281	Total specific costs	CGRSXRG_TA	Pasture and meadow, excluding rough grazings Total area (incl as follow up-crop)
SE025	Total Utilised Agricultural Area	CHEMP_IRA	Hemp Irrigated area
SE080	Total livestock units	CHEMP_SQ	Hemp Sales Quantity
COUNTRY	Country (3 digits FADN acronym)	CHOP_A	Hops Area
		CHOP_OV	Hops Opening Value
		CHOP_TA	Hops Total area (incl as follow up-crop)

B. CAUSAL PROPERTIES FUNCTIONING

In this Appendix we show the correct functioning of the 5 causal properties considered in the paper: i) degree of non-linearity, ii) share of common support, iii) strength of the treatment effect, iv) presence of sample selection bias, and v) presence of latent confounding. Moreover, for each property, we highlight how we control its levels through a parameter - and how this is designed in the R code.

```

1 # Libraries used to run the appendix
  library(broom)
3 library(scales)
  library(Matching)
5 library(MatchIt)
  library(kableExtra)
7 library(tidyverse)

```

B.1 The framework

In our paper, we start from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) dataset for all the EU-28 countries in the year 2020, counting 2864 variables for 81834 observations. Using these real-world covariates, we simulate both an outcome variable and a treatment and compare 9 different machine learning (ML) and econometric methods in retrieving the true treatment effect. As explained in the main paper, three sets of variables enter the framework: the outcome predictors variables X_{OP} , the observed confounders X_{OC} and the latent confounders X_{LC} . More specifically, tables B1-B3 report which variables are included in each set, and also how they are referred to in the analysis.

Table B.1: Treatment determinants

Name	Type	Description
AMCHQP_AD	continuous	Machinery and equipment Accumulated depreciation value
ACSHEQ_CV	continuous	Cash and equivalents closing Value
ALNDAGR_OV	continuous	Agricultural land opening value
ARECV_CV	continuous	Receivables closing value
TF8	categorical	Type of farming

Table B.2: Outcome determinants

Name	Type	Description
NUTS2	categorical	Regional indicator
SE025	continuous	Total utilised agricultural area
SE010	continuous	Total labour input
SE132	continuous	Total output / Total input
SE624	continuous	Total support for rural development

Table B.3: Additional variables

Name	Type	Description
SE042	continuous	Energy crops area
SE621	continuous	Environmental subsidies
SE105	continuous	Table chickens, laying hens and other poultry.
LEGAL	categorical	Legal status
SE281	continuous	Total specific costs
SE446	continuous	Agricultural land, permanent crops, and forest land.

X_{LC} does not enter the simulation processes directly, rather we simulate the two latent confounders ($X_{LC}^{\hat{}}$) entering the equations by linearly combining via `simulate.latent_confounders()` the variables contained in this set. In the subsequent sections, we concentrate on one causal property and its associated parameter at a time, verifying that it functions as intended. To accomplish this, we compare the performances of a regression adjustment (RA) model on the two possible levels each property can take. The behavior of this model is easily interpretable and predictable under the propensity-based assignment, serving as a means to ensure the correctness of the code. Consequently, we only scrutinize the behavior of each causal property under the propensity-based scheme but illustrate the presence of confounding also for the tree-based assignment.

B.2 Presence of confounding

Before starting with causal properties, we must ensure that the way we build our DGPs makes the treatment effect confounded. While this is easier to ensure in the propensity score-based treatment, the tree-based one is more tricky. In order to introduce confounding, under the propensity score assignment we first simulate the outcome using both XOP and XOC, and then use XOC to generate the propensity scores that are used to assign the treatments. Therefore, to ensure that confounding behaves as expected we fit a RA model on an increasing number of controls, expecting the bias to decrease as we add more controls.

```

1   # First package is for propensity based-treatment, second for the tree-
   # based. Then the syntax across them is the same
   load('simulation_erae_package.RData')
3   load('simulation_tree_package.RData')
   # Load dataset and equations to generate the framework
5   dd.w <- read_csv('data_simulation.csv')
   dd <- dd.w %>% mutate(across(.cols= c('NUTS2', 'COUNTRY',
7                                     'TF8', 'countryyear'),
   ~ as.factor(.x))) %>%
9   mutate(ID = rescale(1:81834, to = c(0,1)))

11  sim <- cluster.boot(dd, 1, full = TRUE)
   # Presence of confounding
13  dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
   strength.effect = 0.3,
15   latent = FALSE,
   linear = TRUE,
17   overlap = 0.9,

```

```

                                selection.bias = 0)
19 # No controls
   no.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated) %>% tidy %>% .[2,]
21
   # Few controls
23 few.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
                                NUTS2 + SE025) %>% tidy %>% .[2,]
25
   # All controls
27 all.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
                                NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
                                %>%
29                                tidy %>% .[2,]

31 ### Results
   rbind(no.c, few.c, all.c) %>% rename(estimate = estimate,
33                                term = term) %>%
                                mutate(term = c('No controls',
35                                'Few controls',
                                'All controls'),
37                                estimate = round(estimate, digit = 4),
                                bias = paste(round(((estimate - 0.30)/0.30)*100,
39                                digit = 1), '%')) %>%
                                .[,c(1,2,6)] %>%
41                                kable(., caption = 'Table 5: Bias across specifications with
                                different amount of controls') %>% kable_classic(full_width = F, html_
                                font = 'Cambria')

```

B.3 Presence of confounding

Before starting with causal properties, we must ensure that the way we build our DGPs makes the treatment effect confounded. While this is easier to ensure in the propensity score-based treatment, the tree-based one is more tricky. In order to introduce confounding, under the propensity score assignment we first simulate the outcome using both XOP and XOC, and then use XOC to generate the propensity scores that are used to assign the treatments. Therefore, to ensure that confounding behaves as expected we fit a RA model on an increasing number of controls, expecting the bias to decrease as we add more controls.

```

   # First package is for propensity based-treatment, second for the tree-
   # based. Then the syntax across them is the same
2 load('simulation_erae_package.RData')
   load('simulation_tree_package.RData')
4 # Load dataset and equations to generate the framework
   dd.w <- read_csv('data_simulation.csv')
6 dd <- dd.w %>% mutate(across(.cols= c('NUTS2', 'COUNTRY',
                                'TF8', 'countryyear'),
8                                ~ as.factor(.x))) %>%
   mutate(ID = rescale(1:81834, to = c(0,1)))
10
   sim <- cluster.boot(dd, 1, full = TRUE)
12 # Presence of confounding
   dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,

```

```

14         strength.effect = 0.3,
15         latent = FALSE,
16         linear = TRUE,
17         overlap = 0.9,
18         selection.bias = 0)
19 # No controls
20 no.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated) %>% tidy %>% .[2,]
21
22 # Few controls
23 few.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
24                   NUTS2 +SE025) %>% tidy %>% .[2,]
25
26 # All controls
27 all.c <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
28                   NUTS2 +SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
29 %>%
30         tidy %>% .[2,]
31
32 ### Results
33 rbind(no.c, few.c, all.c) %>% rename(estimate = estimate,
34                                   term = term) %>%
35     mutate(term = c('No controls',
36                    'Few controls',
37                    'All controls'),
38            estimate = round(estimate, digit = 4),
39            bias = paste(round(((estimate - 0.30)/0.30)*100,
40                            digit = 1), '%')) %>%
41     .[,c(1,2,6)] %>%
42     kable(., caption = 'Table 5: Bias across specifications with
43 different amount of controls') %>% kable_classic(full_width = F, html_
44 font = 'Cambria')

```

On the other hand, the tree-based treatment assignment is more intricate. Initially, we employ an unsupervised random forest to cluster observations based on the characteristics in XOC. Subsequently, a straightforward decision tree is utilized to learn these partitions and assign each observation either to treatment or control.

Table B.4: Estimation results

Term	Estimate	Bias
<i>Propensity based assignment</i>		
No controls	0.7319	109.1%
Few controls	0.5048	44.2%
All controls	0.3697	5.6%
<i>Tree based assignment</i>		
No controls	0.6706	91.6%
Few controls	0.3952	12.9%
All controls	0.2557	-26.9%

Despite employing completely different underlying mechanisms, the two procedures achieve

similar results and demonstrate exactly what we expect from them. Indeed, with the inclusion of more (correct) controls, we can better identify the true treatment effect. One observation worth noting is that under the tree-based scheme, even when incorporating all the correct controls, the RA is unable to retrieve the effect due to the underlying non-linearity of the treatment assignment.

B.4 Non-linearity

There are two settings for the degree of non-linearity for both the response and treatment assignment function. The first one is the linear specification, while the second one is highly non-linear and comprises several transformations. See section 4.2 of the main paper for more details of how the non-linear outcome and treatment assignment are computed. To showcase its functioning, we compare the performances of a linear RA model in estimating the treatment effect in both the linear and non-linear scenario. In fact, we expect the model to be unbiased as long as the DGP is linear, while we expect non-linearity to introduce bias.

```

2   # Linear DGP
3   dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
4                                   strength.effect = 0.30,
5                                   latent = FALSE,
6                                   linear = TRUE,
7                                   overlap = 0.9,
8                                   selection.bias = 0)
9
10  linear.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
11                          NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
12  %>%
13    tidy %>% .[2,]
14
15  # Non-linear DGP
16  dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
17                                  strength.effect = 0.30,
18                                  latent = FALSE,
19                                  linear = FALSE,
20                                  overlap = 0.9,
21                                  selection.bias = 0)
22
23  nonlinear.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
24                             NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
25  %>%
26    tidy %>% .[2,]
27
28  ### Results
29  rbind(linear.fit, nonlinear.fit) %>% rename(Estimate = estimate,
30                                             Term = term) %>%
31    mutate(Term = c('Linear',
32                   'Non-linear'),
33           Estimate = round(Estimate, digit = 4),
34           Bias = paste(round(((Estimate - 0.30)/0.30)*100,
35                           digit = 1), '%')) %>%
36    .[,c(1,2,6)] %>%

```

```
kable(., caption = 'Table 5: Bias across different degrees of non-
linearity') %>% kable_classic(full_width = F, html_font = 'Cambria')
```

Table B.5: Linear vs. Non-linear estimates

Term	Estimate	Bias
Linear	0.3697	5.6%
Non-linear	0.0723	-79.3%

The nonlinear scenario introduces a bias close to -79.3% of the true treatment effect.

B.5 Share of common support

The percentage of treated observations on common support is governed via the treatment assignment mechanism, in the `policy.maker()` function.

```
1  policy.maker <- function(data, overlap, share.treat){
3  treated = round(dim(data)[1] * share.treat)
  overlap.diff <- 1 - overlap
5  n <- dim(data)[1]
  # Needs to be ordered so that later on one can remove directly the lowest
  # scores
7  d.sorted <- arrange(data, pi)
  # Rescaling fundamental
9  d.scaled <- d.sorted %>% mutate(pi = rescale(as.numeric(pi), to = c(0.2,
  0.8)))
  # Bernoulli with scores as probability
11 d.treat <- d.scaled %>% mutate(treated = rbernoulli(n, p = pi))
  if(overlap.diff != 0){
13   d.treat$treated <- replace(d.treat$treated, tail(1:n, round(treated*
  overlap.diff)), 1)
  }
15
  # Cond. Stat. to even out the number of treated
17 if (sum(d.treat$treated) >= treated){
  take.back <- sum(d.treat$treated) - treated
19 rejects <- which(d.treat$treated == 1)[1:take.back]
  d.treat <- d.treat %>% mutate(treated = replace(treated, rejects, 0))
21 } else {
  give.out <- treated - sum(d.treat$treated)
23 newcomers <- tail(which(d.treat$treated == 0), n = give.out)
  d.treat <- d.treat %>% mutate(treated = replace(treated, newcomers, 1))
25 }
  d.treat[sample(1:n, n), ]
27 }
```

Through this function, given a number of treatments to be administered, it is possible to assigned them using the propensity scores as the actual probability for each individual to receive the treatment. Common support is a critical assumption for all the models considered

in this analysis - although not that critical for RA. However, a simple plot allows to see exactly how the low and high overlap scenarios differ (Fig B1). A common support level of 90% implies that 90% of the treated observations will have a propensity score falling within the propensity score interval of the control group (same goes with the 50% level).

```
1   # Max overlap
dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
3       strength.effect = 0.30,
       latent = FALSE,
5       linear = TRUE,
       overlap = 0.9,
7       selection.bias = 0)
h.ovl_plot <- dgp %>% ggplot(aes(pi, after_stat(count), fill = as.factor(
   treated))) +
9       geom_density(alpha = 0.3) +
       guides(fill=guide_legend(title="Treatment status")) +
11      geom_vline(xintercept = 0.75, linetype = 'dotted') +
       ggtitle('High overlap') +
13      theme_classic()

15 # 80% overlap
dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
17      strength.effect = 0.30,
       latent = FALSE,
19      linear = TRUE,
       overlap = 0.5,
21      selection.bias = 0)
l.ovl_plot <- dgp %>% ggplot(aes(pi, after_stat(count), fill = as.factor(
   treated))) +
23      geom_density(alpha = 0.3) +
       guides(fill=guide_legend(title="Treatment status")) +
25      geom_vline(xintercept = 0.625, linetype = 'dotted') +
       ggtitle('Low overlap') +
27      theme_classic()

29 h.ovl_plot / l.ovl_plot
```

Figure B.1: High overlap versus low overlap scenarios

B.6 Strength of the treatment effect

The treatment effects in every scenario are heterogeneous, and their values depend on the farming type of the observation (section 4.1) It is computed via the function `simulate.ITEs()`, which allows to the effects to be heterogeneous but at the same time fixing the ATT. As an example, considering the simplest DGP:

```
1   dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
2                                   strength.effect = 0.30,
3                                   latent = FALSE,
4                                   linear = TRUE,
5                                   overlap = 0.5,
6                                   selection.bias = 0)
7 ATT <- dgp %>% filter(treated == 1) %>% .$tau %>% mean
8
9 dgp %>% ggplot(aes(tau)) +
10   geom_density() +
11   geom_vline(xintercept = ATT, col = 'red') +
12   annotate('text', x=0.1, y=2, label = 'ATT = 0.45', angle = 0, col = 'red')
13   +
14   labs(x = 'ITEs',
15        y = 'Density distribution') +
16   theme_classic()
```

Figure B.2: Individual treatment effects distribution

B.7 Presence of sample selection bias

The presence of sample selection bias is regulated with the stratification on the variable S. See section 4.5 of the main paper for more details on how this is achieved.

```
1 # Sample selection bias absent
dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
3                               strength.effect = 0.30,
                               latent = FALSE,
5                               linear = TRUE,
                               overlap = 0.9,
7                               selection.bias = 0)

9 no_sb.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
                               NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
   %>%
11   tidy %>% .[2,]

13 # Sample selection bias present
dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
15                               strength.effect = 0.30,
                               latent = FALSE,
17                               linear = TRUE,
                               overlap = 0.9,
```

```

19             selection.bias = 1)
# Fit without controlling for mediator Z
21 sb.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
                    NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
    %>%
23     tidy %>% .[,2,]

25 # Fit controlling for mediator Z, solving sample selection bias
sb_z.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated + z +
                    NUTS2 + SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
    %>%
27     tidy %>% .[,2,]

29 ### Results
31 rbind(no_sb.fit, sb.fit, sb_z.fit) %>% rename(estimate = estimate,
                    term = term) %>%
33     mutate(term = c('Selection bias absent',
                      'Selection bias present',
                      'Selection bias controlled'),
35             estimate = round(estimate, digit = 4),
37             bias = paste(round(((estimate - 0.30)/0.30)*100,
                              digit = 1), '%')) %>%
39     .[,c(1,2,6)] %>%
    kable(., caption = 'Table 5: Bias when latent confounding is present
') %>% kable_classic(full_width = F, html_font = 'Cambria')

```

Table B.6: Sample selection bias analysis

Term	Estimate	Bias
Sample selection bias absent	0.3697	5.6%
Sample selection bias present	0.3825	-9.3%
Sample selection bias controlled	0.3468	-4%

B.8 Presence of latent confounding

Latent confounding was added to test tree-based models' suggested ability to be able to control unobserved confounders through combinations of controls acting as proxies for them (Bennett and Kallus, 2019; Kallus et al., 2018; Louizos et al., 2017; Wang and Blei, 2019). This gives the researcher a set of controls highly correlated with the latent confounders. To test this ability, we start from X_{LC} to obtain \hat{X}_{LC} : the first set is the one made available to the models, while the second set is the one actually used for the simulation (section 3.2 of the main paper). Here we show that the latent confounders when present are actually confounding the treatment, and also that the tree-based model have access to a good enough representation of them.

```

# Latent confounding absent
2 dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
                                strength.effect = 0.30,
4                                latent = FALSE,
                                linear = TRUE,

```

```

6             overlap = 0.9,
              selection.bias = 0)

8
obs.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
10             NUTS2 +SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
              %>%
              tidy %>% .[2,]

12
# Latent confounding present
14 dgp <- simulate.set_equations(sim,
              strength.effect = 0.30,
16             latent = TRUE,
              linear = TRUE,
18             overlap = 0.9,
              selection.bias = 0)

20
latent.fit <- dgp %>% lm(data = ., mu ~ treated +
22             NUTS2 +SE025 + SE010 + SE132 + SE624 )
              %>%
              tidy %>% .[2,]

24

26 ### Results
rbind(obs.fit, latent.fit) %>% rename(estimate = estimate,
28             Term = term) %>%
              mutate(Term = c('Latent confounding absent',
30             'Latent confounding present'),
              Estimate = round(Estimate, digit = 4),
32             Bias = paste(round(((Estimate - 0.30)/0.30)*100,
              digit = 1), '%')) %>%
34             .[,c(1,2,6)] %>%
              kable(., caption = 'Table 5: Bias when latent confounding is present
') %>% kable_classic(full_width = F, html_font = 'Cambria')

```

B.9 DGP's coefficients

In designing both the response and treatment assignment functions, we start from a fixed coefficient matrix for the main confounders and predictors. The values the coefficients can take in this matrix are bounded between 0.1 and 0.9, and are spaced out evenly across this interval. Then, to derive the coefficients for the squared, cubic, two-way interactions and three way interactions we proceed in the following way:

- squared: starting from a given predictor or a confounder, we draw from a uniform distribution the coefficient for its squared term bounding the minimum and maximum value between respectively half and three quarters of the main coefficient (through the `make_high_order_coeff$squared()` function).
- cubic: same as for the squared term, but the lower and upper bound of the uniform distribution are set at respectively a third and two thirds of the main coefficient (through the `make_high_order_coeff$cubic()` function).

- two-way interaction: same as for the squared terms.
- three-way interaction: same as for the cubic terms.

For a given variable entering both the response and treatment assignment, the main coefficients are set independently - as it also goes for the higher order and interaction terms.

C. SUBSET VERSUS IMPUTATION PSM

Two main versions of propensity score matching (PSM) procedures exist. The first involves subsetting and re-weighting the dataset to balance the covariates, followed by running an additional model to estimate the causal effect (D. Ho et al., 2011b). The second version is used to impute the treated counterfactual outcomes with those of the controls (Abadie and Imbens, 2006, 2016). Before conducting our analysis, we conducted a comparison of the performance of these two methodologies. This comparison involved assessing their effectiveness across all data generating processes (DGPs) in the first bootstrap draw of our analysis. The results of this comparison are presented in table C1.

Table C.1: Comparison of PSM approaches across different DGPs

DGPs	Subset selection PSM	Outcome imputation PSM
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.430	0.242
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.447	0.394
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.581	0.392
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.301	0.305
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.336	0.378
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.451	0.455
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.171	0.528
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.304	0.238
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.438	0.224
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.454	0.388
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.589	0.374
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.301	0.300
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.845	0.390
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.451	0.450
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.980	0.540
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.300	0.300
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.369	0.326
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.450	0.450
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.222	0.467
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.290	0.300
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-1.340	0.584
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.440	0.450
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-1.190	0.734
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.271	0.299
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	-0.092	0.322
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.418	0.450
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.050	0.472
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.279	0.304
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	-1.390	0.624
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.429	0.454
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	-1.240	0.774
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.298	0.244

Considering that the PSM method involving outcome imputation outperformed the subset selection approach, we have decided to discontinue the use of the latter for the remainder of our analysis.

D. CAUSAL FOREST AND CATEGORICAL VARIABLES

In this appendix we assess the robustness of the causal forest (CF) estimates to the exclusion of categorical variables. In the main paper, the DGPs we generated included 2 categorical variables, the region of origin (at NUTS2 level) and the type of farming. However, one of the major drawbacks of CF is their inadequacy in dealing with categorical variables if not properly encoded (Athey et al., 2019). In Johannemann et al. (2019) sufficient representation is suggested as a preferred method for encoding of categoricals. This method aims to find a low dimensional representation of categorical variables containing many groups, while avoiding losing any predictive information. However, a critical assumption in a causal inference setting is that the variables to be encoded should not have a direct causal effect on the outcome - which is violated in our framework. To solve this issue, we resort to a cross-validated target encoding procedure – functioning similarly to sufficient representation. Therefore, we compare the CFs performances across all the 32 DGPs explained in the main paper alternatively including or excluding the categorical variables. First, we remove the categorical variables (NUTS2, TF8) and replace them with their continuous counterparts¹⁵. Second, we use cross-validated targeted encoding (as in the main paper). Thus, we aim at assessing the impact of the introducing categorical variables on CF estimates, and check whether to what extent CF insufficient performance in the main paper can be attributed to the presence categorical variables. The results of this comparison show that although there is a difference in the CF estimated ATT when categorical variables are present or not, the method performances are still insufficient (Table D1). More specifically, when the DGP is non-linear, the estimation bias is doubled by the presence of categorical variables. However, when the DGP is non-linear, the estimation bias when excluding categorical variables is three times the bias of the estimates when categorical variables are encoded.

We believe the intuition behind this estimator behaviour lies in a trade-off between how it attempts to partition the covariate space given by the functional form and categorical variables interaction versus omitted variable bias. It is reasonable to assume that the presence of categorical variables helps the forests dealing better with linearity, by creating a covariate space partition easier to learn by the algorithm. More specifically, a tree-based method assumes a model of the form described in eq. D1, where R_m represents different feature space partitions – which either requires an extremely high number of decision splits or sub-optimally represent a linear function.

$$f(x) = \sum_m^M c_m \cdot \mathbf{1}_{(X \in R_m)} \quad (\text{D.1})$$

However, when categorical variables are added to a linear function the resulting DGPs becomes closer to a step function, consisting in a series of leaps from one category’s linear portion of space to another. Therefore, the better fit to the DGPs could offset the omitted variable bias derived from an imperfect representation and exploitation of the categorical variables. On the other hand, the presence of categorical variables does not improve the fit of the non-linear specifications of both the response and treatment function – since the covariates space already

¹⁵Instead of assigning a coefficient to each group within the categorical variables, we assign a single coefficient to represent the entire variable, and treat the group indicator as a continuous variable. While this transformation eliminates any contextual interpretation of the categorical variables, its effect on the results is negligible since a simulation study allows us to control the DGP.

Table D.1: Comparison of methods across different DGPs

DGP ID	ATT	CVTE	No Categorical	SUF-REP
low.c_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.003	-0.009	-0.003
h.c_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.003	-0.008	-0.003
low.c_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.033	-0.039	-0.033
h.c_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.032	-0.038	-0.032
low.c_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.029	-0.022	-0.029
h.c_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.029	-0.022	-0.029
low.c_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.060	-0.052	-0.060
h.c_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.060	-0.052	-0.060
low.c_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	-0.015	0.020	-0.001	0.020
h.c_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	-0.015	0.021	-0.001	0.021
low.c_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.009	-0.032	-0.009
h.c_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.009	-0.032	-0.009
low.c_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.030	-0.023	-0.030
h.c_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	-0.015	-0.030	-0.023	-0.030
low.c_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.061	-0.053	-0.061
h.c_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	-0.045	-0.061	-0.053	-0.061
low.c_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.015	0.031	0.130	0.031
h.c_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.015	0.037	0.168	0.037
low.c_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.045	0.002	0.099	0.002
h.c_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	-0.045	0.007	0.136	0.007
low.c_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-0.015	0.123	0.193	0.123
h.c_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-0.015	0.165	0.260	0.165
low.c_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-0.045	0.092	0.164	0.092
h.c_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	-0.045	0.135	0.227	0.135
low.c_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	-0.015	0.076	0.234	0.076
h.c_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	-0.015	0.084	0.278	0.084
low.c_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	-0.045	0.043	0.199	0.043
h.c_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	-0.045	0.054	0.248	0.054
low.c_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	-0.015	0.215	0.316	0.215
h.c_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	-0.015	0.260	0.379	0.260
low.c_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	-0.045	0.187	0.287	0.187

takes a structure compatible with tree-based methods. However, the omitted variable bias – although smaller since the contribution of each variable to determining both treatment and response is shared among a larger number of covariates – is still present and drives the results away from the true effect.

E. ADDITIONAL EVALUATION METRICS

E.1 Overall evaluation framework

In this appendix, we show the tables reporting the results across additional metrics we employed to evaluate our models. In particular, the results are evaluated on the basis of two different metrics, applied both on the average and individual treatment effects. First, we rely on the root mean squared error (RMSE) on the ATT (Eq. E1).

$$\text{RMSE}_{ATT} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_m^M \sqrt{(\hat{\tau} - \tau)^2} \quad (\text{E.1})$$

Table E1 provides a quick guide to understand which causal property levels are assigned to each DGP in each row. Each DGP ID (e.g. n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_1) is composed of 5 tags separated by underscores, and each tag represents a causal property. In particular, the ID follows this order: strength of confounding, strength of treatment, latent confounding, overlap, and functional form.

Table E.1: Data generating process (DGP) properties

Property	Levels
Sample selection bias	y.sb: <i>Sample selection bias present</i> n.sb: <i>Sample selection bias absent</i>
Strength of treatment	l.eff: <i>Small treatment effect</i> h.eff: <i>Large treatment effect</i>
Latent confounding	y.lt: <i>Latent confounding present</i> n.lt: <i>Latent confounding absent</i>
Overlap	l.ovl: <i>Low overlap</i> h.ovl: <i>High overlap</i>
Functional form	nl: <i>Non-linear</i> l: <i>Linear</i>

E.2 Tables reporting results by DGPs

Table E.2: RMSE on the ATT – propensity-based assignment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.058	0.051	0.053	0.292	0.062	0.053	0.048	0.292
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.012	0.056	0.054	0.298	0.027	0.184	0.037	0.344
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.068	0.051	0.065	0.279	0.237	0.052	0.057	0.277
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.049	0.053	0.047	0.298	0.041	0.268	0.018	0.291
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.054	0.114	0.049	0.300	0.047	0.064	0.074	0.300
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.054	0.049	0.054	0.299	0.055	0.053	0.058	0.320
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.039	0.025	0.034	0.300	0.034	0.061	0.058	0.300
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.056	0.048	0.055	0.299	0.056	0.056	0.059	0.320
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.058	0.051	0.051	0.095	0.062	0.053	0.048	0.069
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.011	0.054	0.054	0.098	0.027	0.183	0.037	0.037
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.069	0.048	0.070	0.087	0.236	0.052	0.057	0.077
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.043	0.052	0.046	0.099	0.041	0.270	0.018	0.068
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.054	0.112	0.049	0.100	0.047	0.065	0.074	0.100
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.054	0.047	0.054	0.099	0.055	0.053	0.058	0.105
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.039	0.023	0.034	0.100	0.034	0.056	0.058	0.101
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.056	0.050	0.055	0.099	0.056	0.056	0.059	0.104
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.403	0.336	0.142	0.214	1.354	0.079	0.052	0.090
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.013	0.296	0.048	0.210	0.262	0.119	0.030	0.299
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.391	0.359	0.131	0.180	1.654	0.085	0.079	0.098
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.074	0.296	0.052	0.223	0.188	0.264	0.037	0.300
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	3.075	0.287	0.181	0.171	1.345	0.099	0.077	0.087
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.050	0.310	0.073	0.188	1.754	0.053	0.056	0.291
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	1.862	0.261	0.104	0.145	1.044	0.099	0.095	0.091
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.070	0.304	0.056	0.199	1.183	0.073	0.065	0.291
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.333	0.123	0.038	0.064	1.245	0.080	0.052	0.091

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.011	0.097	0.045	0.074	0.262	0.117	0.030	0.100
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.320	0.151	0.021	0.065	1.033	0.085	0.079	0.099
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.071	0.096	0.050	0.122	0.188	0.274	0.037	0.097
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	1.911	0.101	0.080	0.128	1.832	0.100	0.077	0.088
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.055	0.107	0.045	0.108	1.755	0.057	0.056	0.096
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	2.486	0.070	0.062	0.086	1.574	0.099	0.094	0.092
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.074	0.104	0.060	0.080	1.182	0.073	0.065	0.096

Table E.3: RMSE on the ATT – tree-based assignment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.094	0.294	0.084	0.295	0.026	0.118	0.116	0.328
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.065	0.299	0.117	0.297	0.064	0.080	0.102	0.361
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.095	0.293	0.093	0.293	0.026	0.118	0.116	0.328
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.065	0.299	0.132	0.298	0.064	0.080	0.102	0.361
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.278	0.301	0.257	0.301	0.073	0.378	0.327	1.179
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	1.08×10^{82}	7.32×10^{82}	6.41×10^{82}	8.95×10^{82}	3.27×10^{82}	1.91×10^{83}	3.37×10^{82}	2.34×10^{83}
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.290	0.301	0.276	0.300	0.073	0.387	0.327	1.179
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	1.08×10^{82}	9.43×10^{82}	5.21×10^{82}	9.93×10^{82}	8.32×10^{82}	1.65×10^{83}	3.37×10^{82}	2.34×10^{83}
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.104	0.097	0.096	0.098	0.026	0.118	0.116	0.123
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.079	0.099	0.123	0.100	0.064	0.079	0.102	0.167
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.104	0.097	0.093	0.097	0.026	0.117	0.116	0.123
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.079	0.099	0.120	0.098	0.064	0.081	0.102	0.167
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.252	0.109	0.229	0.100	0.073	0.401	0.326	0.748
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	1.36×10^{82}	1.02×10^{83}	6.21×10^{82}	8.88×10^{82}	9.01×10^{82}	1.81×10^{83}	3.37×10^{82}	2.34×10^{83}

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.267	0.108	0.155	0.100	0.073	0.375	0.326	0.748
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	1.36×10^{82}	7.32×10^{82}	6.45×10^{82}	2.54×10^{82}	7.88×10^{82}	2.14×10^{83}	3.37×10^{82}	2.34×10^{83}
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.168	0.299	0.104	0.050	0.211	0.074	0.116	0.362
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.108	0.299	0.092	0.062	0.269	0.038	0.098	0.382
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.168	0.299	0.105	0.050	0.211	0.074	0.116	0.362
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.108	0.299	0.087	0.064	0.269	0.037	0.098	0.387
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.190	0.296	0.098	0.053	0.582	0.057	0.081	0.439
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.105	0.310	0.088	0.051	0.310	0.033	0.104	0.402
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.190	0.296	0.078	0.048	0.582	0.057	0.081	0.439
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.105	0.310	0.075	0.052	0.310	0.031	0.104	0.402
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.156	0.100	0.091	0.051	0.210	0.074	0.116	0.142
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.094	0.100	0.103	0.064	0.269	0.035	0.098	0.123
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.156	0.100	0.094	0.050	0.210	0.072	0.116	0.142
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.095	0.100	0.106	0.062	0.269	0.041	0.098	0.123
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.134	0.099	0.083	0.045	0.582	0.058	0.081	0.163
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.071	0.109	0.085	0.047	0.311	0.030	0.104	0.132
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.134	0.099	0.083	0.058	0.582	0.061	0.081	0.163
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.071	0.109	0.074	0.055	0.311	0.033	0.104	0.132

Table E.4: Absolute Bias ATT – propensity-based assignment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.191	0.171	0.174	0.972	0.202	0.171	0.153	0.972
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.026	0.184	0.178	0.995	0.086	0.605	0.110	1.143
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.214	0.168	0.200	0.928	0.585	0.145	0.154	0.923

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.155	0.175	0.151	0.993	0.127	0.889	0.046	0.962
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.180	0.379	0.164	0.999	0.156	0.210	0.245	1.002
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.180	0.162	0.178	0.997	0.182	0.174	0.190	1.068
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.130	0.079	0.114	0.999	0.112	0.200	0.191	1.002
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.186	0.152	0.184	0.997	0.186	0.184	0.193	1.066
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.576	0.511	0.502	0.950	0.608	0.511	0.460	0.690
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.081	0.534	0.536	0.980	0.259	1.815	0.331	0.287
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.643	0.483	0.609	0.868	1.760	0.433	0.461	0.770
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.406	0.513	0.450	0.993	0.381	2.687	0.137	0.614
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.539	1.114	0.491	0.998	0.469	0.642	0.736	1.003
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.541	0.469	0.536	0.992	0.545	0.520	0.571	1.052
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.391	0.215	0.343	1.000	0.337	0.538	0.572	1.006
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.559	0.467	0.550	0.993	0.557	0.556	0.578	1.035
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.151	1.120	0.466	0.712	1.127	0.260	0.174	0.294
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.040	0.987	0.129	0.692	0.827	0.361	0.082	0.997
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.957	1.194	0.435	0.587	1.486	0.271	0.254	0.312
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.218	0.988	0.153	0.740	0.577	0.871	0.098	1.001
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	7.987	0.951	0.581	0.559	1.225	0.269	0.198	0.226
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.150	1.032	0.238	0.600	4.682	0.170	0.174	0.972
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	4.995	0.867	0.330	0.406	3.485	0.318	0.297	0.289
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.186	1.014	0.169	0.651	3.755	0.219	0.194	0.968
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	2.357	1.224	0.360	0.580	2.435	0.784	0.522	0.885
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.092	0.965	0.348	0.725	2.485	1.053	0.247	1.001
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	2.440	1.497	0.161	0.564	1.145	0.810	0.763	0.938
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.618	0.958	0.447	1.126	1.736	2.701	0.293	0.970
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	16.086	0.946	0.677	1.186	8.489	0.820	0.594	0.691

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.512	1.074	0.384	0.971	14.054	0.546	0.522	0.962
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	17.159	0.605	0.487	0.694	7.345	0.953	0.892	0.880
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.606	1.042	0.572	0.594	11.267	0.647	0.581	0.957

Table E.5: Absolute Bias ATT – tree-based assignment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.307	0.978	0.277	0.982	0.080	0.385	0.363	1.091
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.193	0.998	0.378	0.991	0.206	0.251	0.318	1.204
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.310	0.977	0.301	0.978	0.080	0.386	0.363	1.091
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.194	0.997	0.406	0.993	0.206	0.251	0.318	1.204
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.738	0.998	0.697	1.002	0.232	1.100	1.039	3.845
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	2.54×10^{82}	1.73×10^{83}	7.32×10^{83}	4.65×10^{83}	3.26×10^{83}	4.50×10^{83}	7.95×10^{82}	5.52×10^{83}
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.727	0.999	0.785	1.001	0.232	1.097	1.039	3.845
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	2.54×10^{82}	2.22×10^{83}	4.76×10^{83}	5.21×10^{83}	3.99×10^{83}	3.89×10^{83}	7.95×10^{82}	5.52×10^{83}
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.026	0.968	0.931	0.980	0.239	1.154	1.088	1.225
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.726	0.989	1.162	0.999	0.617	0.731	0.953	1.666
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	1.024	0.968	0.902	0.966	0.239	1.152	1.088	1.225
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.723	0.987	1.142	0.984	0.617	0.760	0.953	1.666
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	2.086	1.034	1.779	1.000	0.695	3.632	3.118	7.215
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	9.58×10^{82}	7.23×10^{83}	8.58×10^{83}	6.33×10^{83}	2.88×10^{83}	1.28×10^{84}	2.39×10^{83}	1.66×10^{84}
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	2.180	1.028	1.142	0.999	0.695	3.320	3.118	7.215
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	9.58×10^{82}	5.18×10^{83}	2.31×10^{84}	2.11×10^{84}	4.21×10^{83}	1.51×10^{84}	2.39×10^{83}	1.66×10^{84}
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.558	0.997	0.308	0.165	0.639	0.239	0.352	1.205
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.354	0.998	0.275	0.206	0.763	0.112	0.289	1.274

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.557	0.997	0.323	0.166	0.639	0.240	0.352	1.205
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.355	0.997	0.272	0.209	0.763	0.108	0.289	1.289
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.631	0.988	0.257	0.170	1.451	0.176	0.229	1.462
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.328	1.032	0.239	0.168	1.001	0.100	0.325	1.340
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.629	0.986	0.197	0.148	1.451	0.185	0.229	1.462
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.330	1.033	0.207	0.171	1.001	0.093	0.325	1.340
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.556	1.002	0.846	0.507	1.910	0.724	1.055	1.422
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.917	0.997	0.973	0.625	2.293	0.298	0.868	1.218
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	1.550	1.001	0.870	0.496	1.910	0.696	1.055	1.422
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.927	0.997	1.044	0.605	2.293	0.371	0.868	1.218
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	1.324	0.988	0.630	0.419	4.353	0.552	0.686	1.629
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.636	1.088	0.685	0.456	3.009	0.259	0.974	1.320
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	1.313	0.986	0.712	0.504	4.353	0.571	0.686	1.629
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.658	1.088	0.635	0.541	3.009	0.295	0.974	1.320

E.3 CATT-propensity-based treatment

Figure E.1: CATT by DGP 1-18

Figure E.2: CATT by DGP 18-32

E.4 CATT- tree-based treatment

Figure E.3: CATT by DGP 1-18

Figure E.4: CATT by DGP 18-32

F. SMALL SAMPLE SIZE RESULTS

Figure F.1: Percentage bias across different causal properties for small sample size

Figure F.2: CATT by DGP 1-18

Figure F.3: CATT by DGP 18-32

Figure F.4: CATT by DGP 1-18

Figure F.5: CATT by DGP 18-32

Table F.1: Root mean squared error on the average treatment on the treated for the propensity-based treatment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.066	0.198	0.049	0.144	0.059	0.047	0.062	0.293
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.051	0.225	0.074	0.095	0.062	0.029	0.080	0.378
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.066	0.198	0.053	0.148	0.096	0.048	0.066	0.278
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.053	0.221	0.077	0.095	0.091	0.046	0.080	0.430
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.063	0.272	0.058	0.131	0.069	0.064	0.075	0.301
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.052	0.238	0.051	0.208	0.061	0.055	0.058	0.315
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.070	0.290	0.064	0.113	0.059	0.075	0.099	0.301
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.039	0.255	0.039	0.185	0.031	0.030	0.033	0.313
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.067	0.067	0.051	0.057	0.058	0.049	0.062	0.075
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.052	0.099	0.074	0.051	0.062	0.030	0.080	0.119
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.066	0.069	0.052	0.067	0.094	0.047	0.066	0.074
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.051	0.089	0.070	0.052	0.091	0.046	0.080	0.119
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.063	0.157	0.059	0.081	0.069	0.090	0.075	0.100
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.052	0.088	0.050	0.070	0.062	0.043	0.058	0.104
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.071	0.176	0.064	0.091	0.059	0.074	0.099	0.101
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.039	0.111	0.039	0.074	0.031	0.049	0.033	0.102
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.131	0.125	0.042	0.056	0.239	0.045	0.073	0.298
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.084	0.089	0.084	0.090	0.383	0.036	0.093	0.299
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.160	0.200	0.070	0.065	0.148	0.051	0.078	0.297
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.097	0.099	0.111	0.098	0.288	0.045	0.127	0.309
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.330	0.286	0.092	0.300	1.380	0.202	0.209	0.291
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.100	0.088	0.072	0.091	0.863	0.065	0.067	0.278
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.314	0.352	0.176	0.137	2.247	0.107	0.210	0.289
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.098	0.085	0.063	0.084	0.656	0.050	0.118	0.281
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.118	0.122	0.049	0.061	0.233	0.045	0.072	0.097

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.087	0.096	0.077	0.076	0.382	0.036	0.093	0.100
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.147	0.200	0.076	0.070	0.149	0.050	0.079	0.097
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.099	0.098	0.111	0.095	0.288	0.053	0.127	0.102
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.290	0.243	0.112	0.231	1.380	0.241	0.209	0.096
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.093	0.084	0.075	0.093	0.863	0.049	0.067	0.090
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.316	0.318	0.175	0.134	2.246	0.138	0.210	0.095
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.096	0.074	0.068	0.091	0.657	0.065	0.118	0.091

Table F.2: Root mean squared error on the average treatment on the treated for the tree-based treatment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.202	0.305	0.177	0.160	0.393	0.086	0.127	23462.970
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.536	0.562	0.168	0.204	0.404	0.102	0.224	10834.100
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.202	0.305	0.171	0.183	0.393	0.089	0.127	23462.970
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.536	0.562	0.211	0.200	0.404	0.057	0.224	10834.100
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	1.149	3.155	1.580	0.588	1.904	1.432	3.244	0.611
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	2.12×10^{15}	4.10×10^{16}	3142.465	1469.905	4.81×10^{15}	2.31×10^{15}	1.96×10^{15}	3.20×10^{15}
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	1.149	3.155	2.407	0.497	1.904	1.416	3.244	0.611
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	2.12×10^{15}	4.10×10^{16}	197.843	1322.224	4.81×10^{15}	2.65×10^{15}	1.96×10^{15}	3.20×10^{15}
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.162	0.250	0.140	0.064	0.392	0.078	0.126	12439.890
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.552	0.574	0.105	0.062	0.404	0.068	0.224	8824.876
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.162	0.250	0.071	0.077	0.392	0.081	0.126	12439.890
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.552	0.574	0.117	0.069	0.404	0.069	0.224	8824.876
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	1.174	4.316	1.499	0.142	1.904	1.151	3.244	0.886
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	2.13×10^{15}	4.10×10^{16}	1838.658	943.900	4.81×10^{15}	2.02×10^{15}	1.96×10^{15}	3.20×10^{15}

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	1.174	4.316	1.630	0.559	1.904	1.231	3.244	0.886
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	2.13×10^{15}	4.10×10^{16}	1715.098	639.869	4.81×10^{15}	3.24×10^{13}	1.96×10^{15}	3.20×10^{15}
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.633	0.399	0.136	0.078	9.224	0.116	0.158	34840.220
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	1.065	1.032	0.093	0.133	0.671	0.083	0.165	33359.870
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.633	0.399	0.174	0.090	9.224	0.119	0.158	34840.220
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	1.065	1.032	0.108	0.141	0.671	0.130	0.165	33359.870
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.298	0.424	0.242	0.126	0.686	0.192	0.447	0.443
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.328	0.344	0.201	0.125	0.537	0.126	0.484	0.390
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.298	0.424	0.225	0.098	0.686	0.168	0.447	0.443
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.328	0.344	0.212	0.121	0.537	0.118	0.484	0.390
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.768	0.486	0.138	0.079	8.419	0.122	0.158	19661.290
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	1.149	0.851	0.023	0.056	0.672	0.109	0.165	16819.000
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.768	0.486	0.131	0.100	8.419	0.123	0.158	19661.290
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	1.149	0.851	0.034	0.056	0.672	0.108	0.165	16819.000
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.282	0.320	0.274	0.149	0.686	0.201	0.447	0.193
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.201	0.222	0.240	0.163	0.537	0.132	0.483	0.149
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.282	0.320	0.208	0.106	0.686	0.176	0.447	0.193
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.201	0.222	0.227	0.110	0.537	0.141	0.483	0.149

Table F.3: Absolute bias on the average treatment on the treated for the propensity-based treatment

dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.216	0.580	0.156	0.329	0.170	0.152	0.190	0.974
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.126	0.672	0.215	0.244	0.157	0.082	0.252	1.258
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.206	0.592	0.158	0.361	0.265	0.129	0.165	0.925

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.140	0.664	0.199	0.245	0.277	0.124	0.241	1.419
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.186	0.903	0.170	0.389	0.202	0.202	0.216	1.003
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.166	0.659	0.165	0.530	0.197	0.160	0.146	1.050
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.187	0.962	0.163	0.334	0.181	0.209	0.284	1.003
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.117	0.743	0.117	0.432	0.095	0.086	0.079	1.042
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.671	0.662	0.502	0.537	0.506	0.467	0.564	0.738
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.390	0.894	0.653	0.452	0.471	0.268	0.757	1.140
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.623	0.679	0.484	0.646	0.781	0.384	0.492	0.726
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.429	0.840	0.592	0.500	0.830	0.383	0.722	1.064
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.557	1.160	0.520	0.782	0.606	0.797	0.647	1.003
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.498	0.801	0.493	0.671	0.592	0.352	0.439	1.043
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.572	1.426	0.481	0.807	0.544	0.528	0.851	1.007
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.353	1.036	0.349	0.588	0.287	0.421	0.238	1.024
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.376	0.358	0.127	0.161	0.723	0.141	0.223	0.994
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.256	0.266	0.232	0.250	1.152	0.106	0.191	0.997
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.410	0.586	0.205	0.195	0.382	0.117	0.162	0.990
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.290	0.316	0.329	0.273	0.878	0.116	0.318	1.031
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.892	0.756	0.270	0.834	4.023	0.536	0.554	0.969
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.285	0.217	0.220	0.292	2.723	0.197	0.180	0.926
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.808	0.962	0.456	0.353	6.449	0.309	0.617	0.963
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.311	0.267	0.176	0.245	1.883	0.127	0.347	0.937
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.018	1.088	0.434	0.547	2.104	0.424	0.665	0.970
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	0.782	0.850	0.602	0.636	3.453	0.335	0.571	1.002
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	1.116	1.859	0.655	0.674	1.161	0.338	0.491	0.969
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	0.856	0.956	1.005	0.717	2.639	0.400	0.954	1.018
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	2.397	2.075	1.000	1.945	12.061	2.095	1.661	0.955

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.778	0.534	0.693	0.828	8.169	0.443	0.542	0.895
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	2.311	2.683	1.347	0.929	19.341	1.207	1.851	0.948
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.914	0.693	0.571	0.745	5.666	0.486	1.042	0.911

Table F.4: Absolute bias on the average treatment on the treated for the tree-based treatment

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	0.525	0.992	0.488	0.433	1.239	0.239	0.394	60029.190
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	1.277	1.553	0.526	0.631	1.292	0.318	0.443	28354.760
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	0.525	0.992	0.470	0.487	1.239	0.260	0.394	60029.190
n.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	1.277	1.553	0.673	0.614	1.292	0.181	0.443	28354.760
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	3.038	7.390	4.510	1.672	4.286	4.349	9.048	1.814
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	3.17×10^{15}	6.11×10^{16}	5239.329	2450.514	7.16×10^{15}	3.44×10^{15}	2.91×10^{15}	4.77×10^{15}
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	3.038	7.390	6.482	1.514	4.286	4.341	9.048	1.814
n.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	3.17×10^{15}	6.11×10^{16}	331.244	2205.493	7.16×10^{15}	3.95×10^{15}	2.91×10^{15}	4.77×10^{15}
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.098	2.268	1.053	0.570	3.706	0.662	1.177	83347.930
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	3.885	4.201	0.895	0.477	3.874	0.623	1.328	54728.280
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	1.098	2.268	0.623	0.746	3.706	0.680	1.177	83347.930
n.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	3.885	4.201	1.055	0.605	3.874	0.667	1.328	54728.280
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	8.768	29.407	12.894	1.162	12.859	10.594	27.145	7.288
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	9.50×10^{15}	1.83×10^{17}	9198.317	4721.044	2.15×10^{16}	9.03×10^{15}	8.74×10^{15}	1.43×10^{16}
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	8.768	29.407	16.015	4.228	12.859	11.138	27.145	7.288
n.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	9.50×10^{15}	1.83×10^{17}	8582.819	3204.310	2.15×10^{16}	1.45×10^{14}	8.74×10^{15}	1.43×10^{16}
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	1.773	1.276	0.434	0.214	14.193	0.353	0.458	109611.800
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	3.198	3.114	0.280	0.407	2.069	0.233	0.460	90726.730

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dgp_id	CF-Theory	CF-Data	BART-Theory	BART-Data	PSM	BART-PSM	CEM	Humble-PSM
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	1.773	1.276	0.564	0.235	14.193	0.319	0.458	109611.800
y.sb_h.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	3.198	3.114	0.352	0.456	2.069	0.347	0.460	90726.730
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	0.958	1.253	0.719	0.348	1.914	0.504	1.377	1.447
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	0.869	1.009	0.530	0.261	1.367	0.368	1.014	1.296
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	0.958	1.253	0.634	0.252	1.914	0.523	1.377	1.447
y.sb_h.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	0.869	1.009	0.555	0.316	1.367	0.345	1.014	1.296
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_l	6.163	4.311	1.241	0.673	38.971	1.111	1.376	164415.200
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_h.ovl_nl	10.234	7.972	0.198	0.497	6.210	0.842	1.376	95700.410
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_l	6.163	4.311	0.979	0.811	38.971	1.008	1.376	164415.200
y.sb_l.ef_nlt_l.ovl_nl	10.234	7.972	0.322	0.506	6.210	0.748	1.376	95700.410
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_l	2.711	2.996	2.521	1.237	5.741	1.745	4.129	1.736
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_h.ovl_nl	1.844	1.779	1.943	1.386	4.101	1.245	3.040	1.429
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_l	2.711	2.996	1.711	0.892	5.741	1.362	4.129	1.736
y.sb_l.ef_ylt_l.ovl_nl	1.844	1.779	1.838	0.768	4.101	1.215	3.040	1.429

G. BIAS-VARIANCE TRADE-OFF

Figure G1 reports the bias-variance plot for each of the method across all scenarios. The biases as well as the variances have been normalized by dividing each of them respectively by the maximum absolute value they had to preserve the relative distance between each point. This is done to obtain a more compact graph, and since the objective of this plot is to show the correlation between bias and variance rather than their magnitude.

Figure G.1: Bias-variance trade-off for each method across all scenarios

H. METHOD SENSITIVITY TO COMMON SUPPORT

Table H1 presents the bias for all methods across various shares of common support in both linear and non-linear DGPs, where the treatment effect is large, and both sample selection bias and latent confounding are absent.

Table H.1: Method performance by linearity and overlap

Overlap	Linear				Non-linear			
	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
CF-Theory	-0.05	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.01	0.10	0.03	-0.06
CF-Data	-0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.05	-0.02	-0.10
BART-Theory	-0.15	-0.11	-0.09	-0.02	0.11	0.10	0.07	-0.04
BART-Data	-0.92	-0.97	-0.90	-1.04	-0.92	0.11	0.08	-0.06
PSM	0.41	0.56	0.12	-0.02	0.45	0.32	-0.07	-0.12
BART-PSM	-0.28	-0.09	-0.10	-0.07	-0.29	-0.23	-0.25	-0.25
CEM	-0.16	0.07	0.00	0.00	-0.07	0.07	0.13	0.09
Humble-PSM	-0.93	-0.87	-0.84	-0.87	-1.91	-1.72	-1.46	-1.32
RegAdj	-0.02	0.05	0.00	-0.02	-0.61	-0.53	-0.52	-0.51

As Table H1 illustrates, ML methods maintain nearly a constant level of bias across different shares of common support, indicating their robustness to low overlap as long as it exists. In contrast, classical methods exhibit a significantly higher bias below a certain threshold. Specifically, the bias-corrected PSM registers an almost fourfold increase in bias when the share of common support falls below 50%. Similar trends are observed for BART-PSM and CEM when the share of common support drops below 25%. These results, however, should be viewed as preliminary, and a dedicated simulation is required to thoroughly examine how different shares of common support influence the identification of a causal effect.